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GRAPHITE STRATIFICATION BY MICROCLUSTER WATER IN A MAGNETIC FIELD

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Abstract

The article proposes a model of graphite exfoliation with microcluster water in a magnetic field and obtaining graphene from it. However, it is impossible to use mechanically obtained graphene on an industrial scale. Therefore, various methods (models) for obtaining graphene have appeared. The proposed model of graphite exfoliation is based on the concept of its surface layer, consisting of three graphene monolayers. Another aspect of the proposed model is the use of a special state of water, namely, the microcluster state, for graphite splitting. Natural graphite practically does not interact with pure water. For a microcluster aqueous solution, an equation is proposed that describes the splitting of graphite in a mobile phase separation system in the presence of a magnetic field and ultrasound. The surface energy of graphite in the interboundary plane is an order of magnitude greater than the surface energy (tension) of microcluster water. But in a magnetic field with ultrasound, the surface tension of microcluster water increases sharply, which leads to the exfoliation of graphite into graphene sheets.

Keywords: model, intercalation, graphite, graphene, magnetic field, water clusters

Introduction

Delamination (intercalation) of layered crystals using mica (muscovite - $\text{KAl}_3\text{Si}_3\text{O}_{12}\text{H}_2$) as an example was used by I.V. Obreimov back in 1930 [1] to determine the surface energy and adhesion energy of mica crystals. This method was implemented at a higher level in [2] and by us theoretically in [3]. In the cleavage plane, the adhesion energy for mica is: $W_{aa} = 0.809 \text{ J/m}^2$ [3]; $W_{aa} = 0.81 \pm 0.38 \text{ J/m}^2$ [3]; $W_{aa} = 0.76 \text{ J/m}^2$ [1]. All measurements are equal within the error. Delamination of layered graphite crystals was carried out mechanically using adhesive tape in 2004 [4]. A single-layer graphite sheet is called graphene. To date, many methods have been invented for producing graphene sheets, both single-layer and multilayer [5]. There are methods for exfoliating graphite into graphene sheets:

1. Mechanical cleavage.
2. Thermal cleavage.
3. Ultrasonic cleavage.
4. Chemical cleavage.
5. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD).
6. Epitaxial growth.
7. Electrochemical intercalation.
8. Dissociative evaporation.
9. Plasma electrochemical cleavage.

The basis of all these methods is to increase the distance between layers (preferably pure natural graphite) by acting on the graphite itself using physical (ultrasound, etc.) or chemical (electrochemical intercalation, etc.) fields. However, it is impossible to use graphene obtained mechanically on an industrial scale.

We also proposed a method for exfoliation of layered graphite crystals with microcluster water [6], the theory of which is proposed in articles [7, 8].

The aim of this work is to construct a model of splitting layered graphite using water in a microcluster state in a magnetic field and obtaining graphene sheets from it.

Thickness of the surface layer of graphite

Graphite is a thermodynamically stable sp^2 -hybridized allotropic modification of carbon. Usually, its density in the natural mineral is within 2260 kg/m^3 , and in the artificial one it is $1650 - 1750 \text{ kg/m}^3$, which is due to its significant porosity. The structure of the graphite crystal is alternately hexagonal layers of carbon atoms [9], which are located parallel to each other (Fig. 1a). Carbon atoms located in the basal planes are more strongly bonded to carbon atoms in neighboring planes. This is what causes the anisotropy of the crystal lattice. The bond energy between the graphite layers is an order of magnitude less than the bond energy of the atoms in the basal planes. It is precisely by breaking these bonds that the graphite splits. The structure of the graphite layers is shown in Fig. 1b, constructed according to the methodology of our work [10].

According to the article [10], the nanolayer $R(I)$ is expressed by the ratio:

$$R(I) = \beta \cdot \frac{m}{\rho \cdot S} \text{ [m]}. \quad (1)$$

Here m is the molar mass of carbon; ρ is its density; $S = 1 \text{ m}^2$ is the area of the nanolayer; $\beta = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Knowing the values in formula (1), we calculate the thickness of the nanolayer (Table 1).

Figure 1. Graphite structure [9] (a); graphite layer structure [10] (b).

Table 1.

Thickness of the R(I) graphite nanolayer [11].

Carbon	Symmetry	m, kg/mol	ρ , kg/m ³	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm
Graphite	C6/mmc-D ⁴ _{6h}	12011	2260	0.90 (3)	2.46 (3)

Table 1 shows that the graphite nanolayer (Fig. 1a) is a 2D nanostructure with dimensions of (0.9 × 2.46) nm, which meets the Gleiter criterion [12]. The number of graphene monolayers in graphite is given in brackets in Table 1, which turned out to be three. This is confirmed by experimental data (Fig. 2). All the graphs in Fig. 2 show that if the number of graphene monolayers exceeds 3, then the graphene sheet turns into graphite. This fact is confirmed by our model, which is described by the relation (1)/

We now present the relationships obtained in the article [10]:

$$A(z) = A(\infty) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{z}\right), \quad R(I) < z < R(II) \tag{2}$$

$$A(z) = A(\infty) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + z}\right), \quad 0 < z < R(I).$$

In equation (2), the value A(z) is a property of the graphite nanolayer and mesolayer; A(∞) is a property of the graphite volume (Fig. 1 b). In the graphite nanolayer, as in all nanostructures, a size effect is observed, so that the surface energy in this layer is equal to γ_1 [18]:

From equation (3) it follows that the surface energy of a graphite monolayer is two times less than the surface energy of the bulk phase of graphite. From this follows the fact that in order to displace a graphite nanolayer relative to the rest of the bulk phase, it is necessary to apply an adhesive energy equal to [19]:

$$W_a \approx 1.5 \cdot \gamma_2, \tag{4}$$

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + z}\right) \approx 0,5\gamma_2, \tag{3}$$

a)

b)

Figure 2. The number of graphene monolayers according to the data of works [14-17]

We will estimate the stresses σ_{ii} that arise between phases γ_1 and γ_2 using the relations [19]:

$$\sigma_i = \sqrt{W_a \cdot \dot{L} / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

In equation (5), the value of E is Young's modulus. Then, using (5), we can estimate the mechanical quantities for graphite.

Table 2.

Mechanical quantities for graphitera

Carbon	W_{aa} , mJ/m ²	W_{ac} , mJ/m ²	σ_{Ha} , GPa	σ_{Hc} , GPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
Graphite	3613	798	5,74	1,37	7,59	3,48

Water in a microcluster state

Natural graphite does not interact with pure water, because the size of a water molecule exceeds the size of the interplanar distance [20]. At the end of the last century, researcher Jordan K. proposed a model of water, which consisted of six water molecules [21]. He

called this model a "quantum of water" or a water cluster. After this, hundreds of works were devoted to the cluster model of water, a review of which is given in the articles [22-24].

It turned out, as confirmed by computer calculations, that microcluster water contains from 3 to 50 units of water molecules (Fig. 3) [25].

Figure 3. Microcluster water [25].

We will briefly describe the process of creating clusters in the structure of water [26, 27]. Pure water, preferably without foreign impurities, is heated to a state of steam and this steam is passed through a membrane in a magnetic field. Next, this water vapor condenses in the presence of IR or UV radiation. To stabilize the entire process, a metasilicate salt is added to the condensed steam at 1%. The fact that microcluster water has been obtained is determined by the method of nuclear magnetic resonance at a frequency of 115 Hz [26, 27].

In the work [28], the microcluster water model was subjected to serious criticism, the basis of which is the discovered fact that the NMR spectrum does not depend on the number of molecules in water, but is determined by the pH of the solution. According to the author of the work [28], microcluster water, in essence, contradicts the fundamental laws of chemistry.

Let us now outline our approach to clusters in water. First, we note the work of Rusanov [29], according to which the surface layer of water is understood as a layer 1-2 nm in size. According to Jordan's work [21], the surface layer of water contains 6 molecules, i.e. has a size of $(6 \times 0.195 = 1.15 \text{ nm})$. Using the experimental data, we calculate $R(I)$ using formula (1) at $T = 298 \text{ K}$; $\gamma = 72.8 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ (J/m}^2\text{)}$; $\nu = 18 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ (m}^3\text{/mol)}$; $R_0 = 8.31 \text{ (J/K mol)}$; $R(I) = 1.1 \text{ nm}$ [30]. In other words, the number of molecules in this layer is also 6. Thus, our model (1) and the models of Rusanov and Jordan indicate a cluster structure of the surface layer of water, the mixing of which leads to a cluster structure of the entire liquid. Whether this water structure is preserved without external influences is a question that requires further research.

Modeling the movement of microcluster water through graphite in a magnetic field with a moving phase boundary

Let microcluster water with a density $u(r,z,t)$ move in a cylindrical vessel containing graphite with a moving phase boundary according to the law $\alpha(t)$. This problem is similar to the Stefan problem.

$$\frac{\partial u(r,z,t)}{\partial t} = d \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 u(r,z,t)}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial u(r,z,t)}{\partial r} \right) \right]. \quad (6)$$

Here d is the diffusion coefficient of microcluster water. The boundary conditions in the cylindrical coordinate system will be as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u(r,z,t)|_{t=0} &= f(r,z), \\ u(r,z,t)|_{r=R} &= \eta(z,t), \\ u(r,z,t)|_{z=0} &= \eta_1(r,t), \\ u(r,z,t)|_{z=\alpha(t)} &= \eta_2(r,t), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The final solution to problem (6-7) will look like this:

$$\begin{aligned} u(r,z,t) = & J_0\left(\frac{2r}{R}\right) e^{-a^2 t} \left\{ \frac{e^2 J_0\left(\frac{2r}{R}\right)}{16a^3} \ln t + \frac{LJ_1\left(\frac{2r}{R}\right)}{16a^3} e^{-a^2 t} \ln(t-1) \right. \\ & \left. + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}}\right) \left(\frac{a^2}{z\pi} + \frac{a^3}{\pi^2 z \alpha(t)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}}\right) \frac{2a}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{1}{[z - \alpha(t)]} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In the case when $t \rightarrow \infty$ we have:

$$u(r,z,t) = \frac{d^{3/2}}{\pi^2} J_0\left(\frac{2r}{R}\right) \cdot \frac{t}{z \alpha(t)}, \quad (9)$$

Flat $z = V t$, where V is the speed of microcluster water, during which it moves in time t , while $\alpha(t) = \alpha_0 t$. If we use the asymptotics of the Bessel function, then we have:

$$u(r,z,t) = \frac{d^{3/2}}{\pi^{5/2}} \cdot \frac{1}{V \cdot \alpha_0 \cdot t}, \quad (10)$$

When the interplanar distance in graphite is filled with microcluster water, the velocity V drops to zero and then the density of the aqueous solution will be equal to its maximum value:

$$u = u_{\max} \left(1 - \frac{V}{V_{\max}} \right), \quad 0 \leq V \leq V_{\max}. \quad (11)$$

The graphs of functions (10) and (11) are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Density u as a function of velocity V (a); Density u as a function of t (b).

In formula (10), we replace the diffusion coefficient d with the kinematic viscosity coefficient χ according to Newton – $d = \chi$. Then, for the response function we have:

$$\chi = \frac{D}{A} \cdot \frac{L}{G^0}. \quad (12)$$

In equation (12), the following notations are introduced: P is the pressure in microcluster water; E is the energy of motion of water molecules; G0 is the Gibbs energy of the graphite+water system; B = const. The graph of equation (12) is shown in Fig. 5a. The Gibbs energy of the graphite+water system is $G^0 = \gamma s$, where γ is the surface tension of the graphite+water system; s

Figure 5. Graph of the linear function of viscosity χ versus pressure (a); graph of function (13) (b)

We write equation (13) as:

$$W_D = \cdot 10^3 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{L_N}{\check{E} \cdot \check{v} \cdot t} \cdot \frac{L_N}{\check{E} \cdot \check{v} \cdot t}}, \quad (14)$$

For the system "graphite + water" the values are $Y = 2 \cdot 10^{-8}$, $\alpha_0 = 0.2$.

Intercalation of water into graphite and its subsequent stratification is possible when the following relations are fulfilled:

$$\begin{aligned} W(C) - W(H_2O) &\rightarrow \min, \\ \gamma(C) - \gamma(H_2O) &\rightarrow \min, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where $\gamma(C) = 798 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ is the energy of the graphite surface in the c plane; $\gamma(H_2O) = 72.8 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ is the surface tension of water.

is its area (Fig. 5b). Then, equation (12) can be rewritten in a generalized form:

$$\chi = \frac{Y}{\gamma}, \quad (13)$$

where Y is the constant of the system "graphite + water"/

Equation (15) shows that any effect on water (chemical impurities, vibration, ultrasound, electric and magnetic fields, increased temperature, etc.) leading to an increase in $\gamma(H_2O)$ will contribute to the exfoliation of graphite.

Effect of magnetic field on the value of $\gamma(H_2O)$

In work [31], a system of permanent magnets mounted on a piezoelectric plate was used to activate water to modulate the magnetic field. The conductivity and permittivity of water activated by this source were experimentally studied. The effect of a magnetic field on bidistilled water ($0.84 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ Ohm-1m-1}$) leads to an increase in surface tension with an increase in the magnitude of the tension (Table 3).

Table 3.

Parameters of bidistillate in a magnetic field [31]

Magnetic field, T	pH		Surface tension		Dielectric constant	
	fractions of a unit	%	10^{-3} N/m	%	F/m	%
0.19	0.35	5.1	1.6	2.2	1.5	1.8
0.35	0.44	6.4	3.7	5.1	1.4	1.7
0.48	0.62	9.1	4.7	6.4	1.4	1.7
0.57	0.62	9.1	5.3	7.3	1.4	1.7

Table 3 shows that $\gamma(H_2O)$ increases with a three-fold change in magnetic field strength, i.e. linearly: $\gamma(H_2O) = \mu H$, where μ is the proportionality coefficient and H is the magnetic field strength. Since in our case $\mu = 3$, equation (15) yields: $\gamma(C) - 3H = 0$ and $H \approx 0.3 \text{ T}$. At such a magnetic field strength, graphite can be exfoliated with microcluster water.

Thus, using equations (6) – (15), it is possible to obtain exfoliation of graphite with microcluster water in a magnetic field and obtain single-layer graphene in an environmentally friendly way.

Conclusion

Graphene, created 21 years ago, is a unique material that is destined to become the substance of the 21st century. Graphene has a wide variety of applications. The global graphene market began to grow only five years ago, which was due to the high cost of graphene.

The method we proposed for obtaining graphene from graphite using microcluster water deserves further study, since it can provide an environmentally friendly and reliable method for obtaining a high-volume initial product.

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